

STUDY OF FORMAL AND INFORMAL SPEECH ETIQUETTES

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ABSTRACT: This article talks about formal and informal speech etiquette and their role in society. The study of Uzbek and German speech etiquette rules will be analyzed.

KEY WORDS: society, etiquette, communication, ethics, behavior.

As long as a person lives in a certain society, it is impossible to imagine his life without communication. Communication is a tool for receiving, exchanging messages among people, conveying one's opinion to others. When a person communicates, he/she inevitably encounters the rules of speech etiquette. It is not difficult to understand which stratum of society the speaker belongs to by his speech and behavior. Before talking about "speech ethics", we should know what the term "Ethics" means. The concept of "etiquette" is derived from the French word "etiquette" and means "form of behavior", "rules of politeness and respect". Generally speaking, etiquette is the rules of etiquette that are used by representatives of different levels of society and regulate the relationship between them. Ethics is divided into several parts depending on its content. Including speech ethics, eating, dressing ethics, etc. It is said that in the old days, in the palace of the great French king Louis XIV, potatoes were distributed to the invited guests, describing how to behave around the table and with other guests, and these potatoes were called "etiquettes". Speech etiquette is considered a part of ethics and is important in society and people's lives.

The study of speech etiquette has always attracted the attention of linguists. The study of speech etiquette began in the second half of the 20th century. V.S. Kostamorov's article entitled "Russky rechevoy label" published in 1957 was the introduction to research in this direction. From the same period, a special direction of linguistic knowledge - speech etiquette appeared" [1,502]. Many linguists have conducted scientific research on speech etiquette in world linguistics. Among them, A.Knigge, R.Sedlashek, N.M.Firsova, R.Luelbgoyfts, V.Hartung, Y.D.Desheriev, H.Schonfeld, B.Jurgen, S.Augenstein, A.A.Akishina, V.M.Alpatov, N.D.Arutyunova, B.N.Golovin, V.E.Goldin, V.G.Kostomarov, N.F.Mikheyeva, T.N.Naumova, F.Pap, L.P.Stupin, K.S.Ignatev, N.I.Formanovskaya, B.Kim, V.Bredov, I.Renate, Sh.James, K.Rainer, H.Luger, J.Mala, Scientists such as Sh.Friedmann, J.Schild have carried out scientific-research works on this topic, which are important in world linguistics. They studied speech etiquette units in German, Japanese, English, Russian, Spanish, and French languages. S.Ibrohimov, R.Kongurov, Kh.Doniyorov laid the foundation stone for the theoretical research of speech culture and speech habits in Uzbek and its formation as a separate field in linguistics, while E.Begmatov, A.Major Scientists such as Rustamov and N.Mahmudov mainly worked on lexical units and parts of speech. B.Orinboyev in the field of syntax, in the studies of scientists such as E.Begmatov, Y.Tajiyev, S.Mo'minov, S.Karimov, Sh.Iskandarova, Z.Akbarova

and K.Kakharov, the issue of analysis of the communication process in terms of forms of speech habits was clarified." [2,18]

N. Ulokov in the book "Theory of Linguistics" notes that Ferdinand de Saussure founded systematic linguistics in the 20th century, after which dozens of new linguistic currents and schools emerged. "In order to more clearly define the boundaries and subject of linguistics, Ferdinand de Saussure, like Wilhelm von Humboldt, used the method of antonym (contrast) to separate language and speech and put them in opposition to each other. According to him, language is only one aspect of speech activity. Language is the opposite of speech. The main difference between language and speech is that language is a social phenomenon, and speech is an individual phenomenon. [6,9]

Uzbek linguist Zuhro Akbarova studied the language from a sociolinguistic point of view, that is, the social nature of the language, its social functions, and at the same time, she conducted research on forms of address, which are one of the main factors of speech, and the place of address in the relationship between thought and language. , in his scientific work, he expressed important information about the general and specific features of address and motivation, the role of gestures and color in the expression of appeal, the psycholinguistic function of appeal. In his opinion, "thinking affects the formation of speech in all its forms and forms. Therefore, the transformation of thought into real reality depends on the language, the realization of the language - the acquisition of concreteness in the speech style depends on the factor of thinking. [2.7]

Sh.Gulyamova in her dissertation entitled "Gender characteristics of Uzbek language euphemisms" conducted research on the role of euphemisms in the speech of Uzbek men and women, provided information about the factors causing divided into groups the emergence of euphemisms, and gender euphemisms. M. Hakimov mentions in his monograph "Fundamentals of Uzbek pragmalinguistics" that the study of issues related to human speech activity is of great scientific and theoretical importance. "Modern linguistics consists of branches of extralinguistics, intralinguistics and comparativistics, all of which study human speech activity. Along with the human thought, his spiritual world finds its expression in the speech. Research and analysis of overt and hidden meanings in speech, studying issues such as how a person manifests his identity through his speech plays an important role in opening up the concepts of today's Uzbek way of thinking, national ideology and national idea. [4,5] As in every nation, German linguists have been confused about the rules of German speech etiquette for a long time. Due to the fact that the German state is among the most developed countries in Europe, we can say that scientific research on speech etiquette began a little earlier than the Uzbek people. The famous German writer, cultural scientist Adolf Freier von Knigge also wrote a great work in this field, which is necessary for the German people. The book "Über den Umgang mit Menschen" (About communication with people), published for the first time in 1788, brought fame to A.F. Knigge during his lifetime. This book contains important aspects of the communication process, i.e. rules of etiquette. This book, consisting of 3 parts and 26 chapters, was later called "Knigge", "Knigge rules" after the author's name. In the book "Allgemeine Bemerkungen und Vortschriften" (General remarks and rules), "Über den Umgang mit sich selbst" (On dealing with oneself), "den Umgang mit Geistlichen", "Eltern, Kindern und Blutsverwandten" , there are chapters called "Eheleuten", "Verliebten", "Hauswirten, Nachbarn" (Communication with priests, parents, children, relatives, spouses, lovers, masters and neighbors).The book ends with notes on how to deal with animals and the

relationship between writer and reader. Learning the language of young people has been a research object of German linguists. Especially Susanne Augenstein in her "Funktionen von Jugendsprache" (Functions of Youth Language), "Studien zu

Journal of Innovations in Social Sciences Researches such as verschiedenen Gesprächstypen des Dialogs Jugendlicher mit Erwachsenen" (Study of different types of conversations between young people and teenagers) has made a significant contribution to this field. In addition, scholars such as Sedlaczek R. "Das Lexikon der Jugendsprache" (Lexicon of the Language of Youth), Bredow W. "Medien und Gesellschaft" (Media and Society), Lüger H. "Pressesprache" (Language of the Press) Those who have conducted research on the indicated topics.

Until now, almost no research has been conducted on the rules of German and Uzbek speech etiquette, but Q.Kakharov found a solution to this problem in his dissertation "Comparative study of Uzbek and German speech etiquettes". In this scientific work, the similarities and differences in the speech etiquettes formed in the Uzbek and German languages, the unique aspects of culture and speech processes between the two peoples, the use of Uzbek and German forms of address, non-verbal means related to age and gender in the communication process have been studied within the framework of two languages. "Speech etiquettes used by Uzbeks in the process of communication were mainly formed under the influence of Eastern culture, and speech habits used in the process of German communication were formed under the influence of Western culture. A comparative study of the speech etiquettes of both nations will have a certain effect on the linguistics of these nations. The work and important decisions of our president in the development of the Uzbek language are of great importance for the development of the Uzbek language. On October 21, 2021, a ceremony dedicated to the thirtieth anniversary of the granting of the status of the state language to the Uzbek language was held at the International Congress Center, and the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev participated in this ceremony and gave a speech. . "The Uzbek language, one of the oldest and richest languages in the world, is a symbol of our national identity and independent statehood, a priceless spiritual wealth, a great value for our people. If anyone wants to feel the grace, charm and power of the Uzbek language, and its limitless possibilities, he should listen to the legends of our mothers, our thousand-year-old epics, our immortal statuses, and listen to the magical songs of our bakhshi and hafiz - says the honorable President.

In conclusion, we can say that the place of speech etiquette in our life is incomparable, therefore scientific research on speech etiquette has great importance in linguistics. It is worth noting that there are many advantages of the scientific works conducted in the framework of two languages. The more the rules of speech etiquette of two or more languages are studied, the more it is considered an achievement for science. With this, friendship and cooperation between countries and nations is strengthened, it is very important both socially and economically, and for the science of world linguistics.

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